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ISAC Architecture and Sensing Topology Switching in 6G Cellular Networks

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Abstract — Integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) is one of the candidate technologies with promising potential for the sixth generation (6G) of wireless networks. This article presents an overview and comparison of the sensing topologies considered for ISAC: monostatic, quasi-monostatic, bistatic and multistatic. We also describe the ISAC architecture with control and processing functions and introduce a new framework that allows topology switching. The proposed switching framework uses the sensing results of a sensing session to assist the ISAC control function to decide whether the current topology should be retained or switched to a different one, in order to maintain optimal sensing performance. Using simulations, we compare various sensing performance indicators, such as received power and angle-of-arrival estimates, across ISAC topologies that are candidates for switching. According to our simulation results, switching to the bistatic sensing topology delivers the best performance, considering deployment and radio conditions.

Keywords — ISAC, Topology, Network Architecture, Switching, 6G.

I. INTRODUCTION AND CHALLENGES

Integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) is a promising technology for the next generation of mobile communication systems that has been in the focus of academic and industrial research efforts in recent years. It has also been recommended by the International Telecommunication Union Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R) industry regulations for the International Mobile Telecommunications Networks-2030 (IMT-2030) [1].

ISAC integrates the sensing and spatial localization of passive (i.e., not connected) objects into the set of mobile broadband services provided by cellular networks, expanding the network's functionality beyond the known connectivity and communication services. An essential aspect of ISAC is the support of a new sensing capability in the cellular network to detect and track passive objects, including pedestrians, non-connected terminals, drones, vehicles, and vulnerable road users. ISAC networks can also communicate the sensing results – reflecting the properties of detected objects (e.g., presence or absence detection, feature extraction, location, velocity, environmental conditions detection, etc.) – along with supplementary information, such as environment information or area size, to the network (Fig.1). Indeed, cellular networks with sensing capabilities are sometimes referred to as perceptive networks [2].

In terms of technology, RADAR is the traditional approach to location estimation and sensing. Unlike 5G-based location approaches that rely on

communication signals and waveforms, RADAR signaling is specifically tailored for localization and sensing and utilizes specific correlation and ambiguity function attributes. In fact, in RADAR sensing methods, the position of the passive object (target) is estimated based on the range, angle and Doppler shift of the RADAR signal at the reference point. To do so, several measurements are collected by the receiver, such as angular values, location values and Doppler shift, based on which suitable location and velocity determination algorithms are applied using databases of reference points [3].

Fig.1 ISAC scenarios in perceptive cellular networks.

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has recently been studying the relevant use cases and channel models that will enable ISAC in cellular networks. A study on ISAC use cases is described in [4], and a study on channel modelling for ISAC for NR is being undertaken [5]. Based on the progress made by 3GPP in RAN#105 meeting, it is very likely that ISAC will become a technology adopted in the next 6G wireless standards [6].

ISAC in cellular networks can be performed in a monostatic topology, where the transmitter and the receiver sensing antennas are located in the same node, or in a bistatic and multistatic topologies, where the transmitter and the receiver sensing antennas are located at different sites [7]. These topologies represent the most common ones for ISAC. Another setup is quasi-monostatic, where the transmitter and the receiver are in the same base station but slightly separated (i.e., quasi-collocated). In Figs. 2 and 3, different ISAC topologies – that involve base station(s) (BS(s)) and user equipment (UE(s)) device(s) – are depicted. It is worth noting that a network deployment may include different ISAC topologies, e.g., where

many BSs in an environment are configured to perform bistatic BS-BS, bistatic BS-UE, multistatic BS-BS-BS or multiple monostatic BSs-based sensing. It is also possible to mix all these topologies with a single BS involved in all of them.

Fig. 2: Basic sensing modes involving BS(s): BS-based monostatic sensing in (a), BS-based quasi-monostatic in (b). Tx and Rx denote the sensing transmitter node and the sensing receiver node respectively.

Fig. 3: Different multistatic and bistatic topologies involving BS(s) and UEs: multistatic sensing with M transmitter and N receiver sensing antennas in (a), BS-BS bistatic sensing in (b), UE-BS bistatic sensing in (c), and BS-UE bistatic sensing in (d).

Identification of the most suitable sensing topology is a challenge that depends upon several factors such as use-case, network capabilities, deployment characteristics and sensing area coverage. Furthermore, an ISAC architecture encompassing the necessary sensing functions for control and processing should be in place to obtain and evaluate the sensing results from a given topology. This evaluation should be continuous during the whole sensing session to determine if the sensing requirements regarding, e.g., accuracy and latency, are satisfied by a given topology and not deteriorated if an event occurs. In fact, if we take the example of the mobility of a passive object as event, this can lead to a change in the resources allocated to the sensing BS. While this change has similarities to cellular handovers (e.g., in 4G LTE or 5G NR handovers), as it involves two BSs acting as source and target, the challenges for ISAC may not be limited to just identifying a suitable target BS to handover the “sensing information” of the passive object to. To handle mobility for ISAC, it further needs to be determined whether a new sensing topology (e.g., monostatic or bistatic) should be activated to provide optimum sensing results and maintain the sensing performance. For instance, it may become necessary to switch from monostatic to bistatic sensing after a mobility event and to activate another BS to increase the sensing range and improve the detection rate. This dynamic topology change with BS(s) activation can be particularly useful at high frequencies and in denser deployments, where continuous tracking and increasing the sensing coverage area by activating different transceivers makes better use of network capacity and reduces latency for moving object detection. Hence, it is crucial to develop a viable

ISAC solution based on an architecture that can meet the sensing requirements [4] and that can be modular to different types of sensing deployments.

To address the above challenges, we first present a comparison of the current ISAC topologies in Section II.A. Section II.B describes the ISAC architecture with procedures for sensing topology selection and switching. Section III provides performance evaluation results on the different sensing topologies, and Section IV draws conclusions.

II. ISAC TOPOLOGIES

A Overview and Comparison of ISAC Topologies

ISAC topologies have different characteristics related to the usage of radio resources and some network limitations.

With monostatic sensing, the transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) are co-located in the same BS and share the same antenna for transmission and reception. This topology may simplify system design, but it requires complex hardware to support in-band full duplex operation to enable simultaneous transmission and reception on the same frequency [8]. It must also implement self-interference cancellation methods, which are costly compared to other ISAC topologies, especially when considering multiple monostatic BSs with massive multiple input multiple output (m-MIMO) systems [9]. Furthermore, monostatic ISAC suffers from phase noise issue, although some mitigation solutions have been investigated recently [10].

In the case of bistatic and multistatic sensing topologies, the ISAC systems comprise two or more Txs and Rxs, respectively, distributed over different BSs. This configuration offers many advantages compared to monostatic ISAC, such as increased sensing range thanks to the involvement of several BSs, improved sensing capabilities, network resilience and reduced vulnerability to interference and jamming. In addition, bi- and multistatic ISAC networks can exploit the advantages of m-MIMO architectures to achieve very high angular resolution, thus improving the sensing accuracy. However, controlled resource coordination is crucial in such topologies, as the Tx and Rx are located in different nodes. In fact, the system must be able to manage both sensing and communication resources, considering different nodes (BSs or UEs) that experience different radio conditions. This may be problematic for a UE sensing node that is located at cell edges, for which resource allocation is more demanding and less flexible. Furthermore, multistatic topology will require very tight inter-node synchronization among all participating sensing-capable BSs to achieve high accuracy and resolution in the sensing process, since sensing needs multiple domains of synchronization: time, frequency, and phase [7].

Another topological option is the quasi-monostatic (or quasi-bistatic) sensing topology, in which the Tx and Rx - which are either the same or separate but closely connected nodes - are co-located and use different sets of antennas. In this configuration, the separation of Tx and Rx reduces the complexity of full duplex and reduces interference, while the close connection enables fast transmission of sensing signals. In fact, the allocations for the Tx and Rx roles can be either permanently assigned or dynamically modified, as the BS locally controls their activation depending on the time of signal reception or transmission. This level of control facilitates interference

management, as coordination between the two antennas is fast and does not require interfacing to or via another node. In addition, the sequence of the interfering signal and the time/frequency allocation are known by the BS, and this information can be quickly made available to its radio branches. However, although the quasi-monostatic topology can be considered less complex than the monostatic scheme, it requires the use of an additional antenna, which increases capital expenditure; and it may be impractical to use at low frequencies due to the large antennas size. In addition, quasi-monostatic range is limited compared with bistatic and multistatic topologies, reducing network capacity and sensing accuracy. Table 1 summarizes the advantages and limitations of the ISAC topologies discussed above.

TABLE 1: SUMMARY OF ISAC TOPOLOGIES COMPARISON.

Topology	Advantages	Limitations
Monostatic	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Existing synchronization between the receiver and the transmitter chain. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Requires new hardware to support real full duplex operation on the same frequency, which is costly (especially with m-MIMO). Limited sensing range to intra-site. Self-interference problem.
Bistatic/ multistatic	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Leverage on m-MIMO to get high angular resolution. No self-interference. Increased sensing range, improved sensing capabilities and reduced vulnerability to jamming. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Higher accuracy requires synchronization between nodes. Resource allocation can become complex in both UL and DL ISAC.
Quasi-monostatic	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced full duplex and self-interference operations. Fast local antenna coordination. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Extra antenna needed at BS, which can increase CAPEX. Impractical to use at low frequencies due to large antenna sizes. Limited sensing range to intra-site.

Fig. 4: Monostatic (Txa, Rxa) pair at Site 1, Quasi-Monostatic (Txa, Rxb) pair at Site 1, Bistatic: (Txa, Rxc) pair at Site 1 and Site 2 respectively.

Practically, a network deployment can consist of one or several BS TxS that are commonly part of different ISAC topologies. Fig. 4 shows an example of such deployment where the monostatic pair is formed by the Txa and Rxa antennas which are co-located. In contrast, the quasi-monostatic pair is formed by Txa and Rxb, which are in the same site but almost

co-located or quasi-located (i.e., not in the same physical equipment, but separated by a marginal distance to reduce self-interference). The bistatic pair is formed by Txa and Rxc, which are hosted in different sites.

B ISAC Architecture and Topology Switching

ISAC systems should be based on an architecture that integrates a number of functions capable to configure an end-to-end sensing task. This will require the interaction of different entities, starting with a sensing unit (SU) embedded in the BS or in a UE. A SU can either transmit the sensing reference signal (SeRS), or receive the signal resulting from the interaction of the signal with the environment (in case of bi/multistatic BS-BS or BS-UE sensing), or both (in case of (quasi)monostatic BS sensing). Each BS can comprise several SUs and covers a geographical area, where the target object can be detected.

The ISAC system includes a Sensing Control Function (SeCF), which is an entity that decides which measurements are needed to satisfy the sensing request, issues the sensing measurement request to SUs and configures a sensing processing function to receive the sensing data from the SUs.

In fact, ISAC systems are likely to be upgraded, compared to 5G networks, with a Sensing Processing Function (SPF) that has processing capability to handle the received sensing data from the SUs. The SPF receives raw data collected by the SUs and processes them into measurement results, ultimately responding to the SeCF request by indicating the outcome of the sensing task. An SPF can be integrated in the SU of the BS, be deployed as a separate entity, or in the same logical equipment as the SeCF. However, due to the sheer volume of raw data that an SPF will have to process, there can be different strategies for its distribution in the ISAC architecture. In fact, depending on the capacity, it can either be realized as a general data processing function in the BS; or is part of a data ingestion architecture for collecting, processing and/or providing data to other entities [11].

Fig. 5: Simplified view of the ISAC network architecture, where an SU can be a network node or a device.

Fig. 5 presents a simplified depiction of the ISAC architecture including SeCF, SPF and SUs. Other functions for data exposure and network privacy may also be defined for, e.g., authenticating and applying policy-based authorization to enable the sensing service in the network. Such functions can be bundled in a function similar to the Network Exposure Function (NEF) defined in 5G [12], but the details of these functions are beyond of the scope of this paper.

The SeCF can initially decide on a sensing topology based on the deployment of different SUs in an area. For example, the locations of Rx/Tx SUs and their coverage area, the availability of sensing-capable UEs and the extent of the sensing target area.

Once the SeCF has configured the SUs with sensing measurement requests according to object characteristics (e.g. meteorological sensing, periodic sensing, object tracking, etc.), it also configures the SPF to receive sensing raw data (e.g. I/Q samples) from the configured SUs and to provide the results of the processing to the SeCF. With respect to the processing step, the requested SUs capture raw data from the sensing area and provide them as input to SPF to process them into measurements results. If there are measurements being processed, such as receiver SeRS power, Time of Arrival (ToA), Line of Sight (LoS), Angle of Arrival (AoA), Signal to Interference and Noise Ratio (SINR), from the SPF, the SPF indicates such results to the SeCF, which may decide on the next action. The SeCF then uses the measurement results obtained to compare them with a benchmark and judges whether the existing topology satisfies the benchmark. In this case, the topology can be maintained, or it can be replaced by another, more efficient topology for the given sensing task.

Fig. 6: Signaling flow for topology selection based on sensing measurement results. Steps 2 and 3 can happen in parallel.

For example, if the sensing target has a potential LoS with a Rx/Tx SU, then a monostatic or quasi-monostatic sensing can be selected by the SeCF, depending on the robustness of self-interference cancellation at the BS. In addition, the target object should not be obscurely positioned with respect to Rx/Tx SU. In such case, reporting AoA measurement would be useful for selecting a next sensing topology in which potential Rx SUs can be omitted when the sensing target object is obscured from the perspective of previously selected Rx SUs. Fig. 6 illustrates the signaling flow of the iterative process.

When performing such iterative filtering of SUs (and BS(s)) based on the results, then bistatic or multistatic topologies may be considered as default for their increased capability and higher detection rate. In such case, the prevailing synchronization error between the candidate Rx/Tx SU can be taken into account to decide between the two sensing topologies. Another criterion to decide would be the sensing target area, i.e., if a larger coverage area is needed then multistatic topology may be considered best. Besides, other input can be considered for the switching mechanism such as any historical information concerning the ISAC topology that has given the best results in a specific area in terms of sensing measurements.

Additionally, the ISAC system may on a continuous basis analyse whether the current sensing topology is performing

well, or if there is need to change the topology based on event detection as shown in flow chart diagram illustrated in Fig. 7

Fig. 7: Triggering of topology change based on event detection.

Different events can be configured upon whose fulfilment can trigger a change in the sensing topology. We list below some examples of events that can be triggered:

- Sensing Quality of Service (QoS):. If the SeCF identifies that the sensing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) which influences Sensing QoS (such as latency, location accuracy, ratio of correct detection to missed and false detection) depletes, then this event would be triggered.
- SeRS received signal strength or quality event: this event is triggered when the SeRS Reference Signal Receiver Power (RSRP) or Quality (RSRQ) or SINR drops below a certain threshold or becomes worse than the SeRS's strength from another Tx SU and may even remain such during a time period. In this case, changing sensing topology may become relevant.
- Mobility event: If the passive object is moving, then further topologies can be configured based upon different combinations of threshold such as RSRP, AoA, Round Trip Time (RTT).

In the next section we evaluate the performance of three ISAC topologies: monostatic, bistatic and quasi-monostatic for different sensing measurements.

III. SIMULATIONS RESULTS FOR ISAC TOPOLOGIES

In the following, MATLAB software was used to perform simulation analysis. We consider the experimental scenario depicted in Fig. 8 where a target is located at the point (x,y) .

Fig. 8: Scenario with bistatic sensing between SU1a and SU2 and quasi-monostatic sensing between SU1a and SU1b. A monostatic sensing capability is assumed at SU1a.

We have two sensing sites: site 1 with sensing unit SU1a and SU1b and site 2 with sensing unit SU2. We consider three sensing settings depicted in Fig. 8:

- Bistatic setting with SU1a as transmitter node and SU2 as receiver node. The transmitter-to-target range and the target-to-receiver range are denoted by $R_{1a,Tx}$ and $R_{2,Rx}$, respectively.
- Quasi-monostatic setting with SU1a as transmitter node and SU1b as receiver node. The transmitter-to-target range and the target-to-receiver range are denoted by $R_{1a,Tx}$ and $R_{1b,Rx}$, respectively.
- Monostatic setting with the transmitter/receiver located both at SU1a. The transmitter-to-target range and the target-to-receiver range are equal to R_{1a} .

TABLE 2: SIMULATION PARAMETER TABLE.

Parameter	Notation	Value
Carrier frequency	f_c	3.5 GHz
SU1a (Tx-s, Rx-s) coordinates	(x_1, y_{1a})	(-10,0) m
SU1b (Rx-s) coordinates	(x_1, y_{1b})	(-10,1) m
SU2 (Rx-s) coordinates	(x_2, y_2)	(10,0) m
Transmit sensing power	P_{Tx}	1 W
Isolation between the sensing Tx and the Rx for monostatic setting	Tx-Rx isolation	{-20,10,0,10,20} dB
Isolation between the sensing Tx and the Rx for quasi-monostatic setting	Tx-Rx isolation	80 dB
Number of sensing Tx antennas	M	16
Number of sensing Rx antenna	N	16
Number of sensing time samples	T_s	64
Antenna gain at the Tx/Rx	G	10 dB
Noise power	σ^2_{noise}	-80 dB
Number of targets	K	1
Radar cross section of the target	σ_{RCS}	2 m ²

In Fig. 9 the received power in dBm at the sensing receiver antenna is plotted with respect to the target's location coordinates on the (x,y)-plane. We observe that equal received power levels at -100 dBm are obtained when the target is located on the red contour, represented by a circle, for the monostatic sensing at the BS1 and on the blue contour, represented by a Cassini-oval [13], for the bistatic sensing. From Fig. 9, we can see that the target's location area resulting in received powers higher than a given level (here at -100 dBm as an example) are given by different regions for monostatic and bistatic sensing.

Fig. 9: Received power in dBm (z-axis) at site 1 and site 2 for respectively monostatic and bistatic sensing set ups versus target's location in (x,y)-plane on the left. The red circle corresponds to the target's locations resulting in equal received power at the BS1 performing monostatic sensing. The blues contour

corresponds to the target's locations resulting in equal received power at the BS2 performing bistatic sensing.

Fig. 10: Received power ratios in dB of monostatic over bistatic sensing. The red line for $z=0$ dB (ratio equal to 1 in linear scale) corresponds to the equal received powers for the two sensing modes.

In Fig. 10, the ratio between the monostatic over bistatic received powers in dB is plotted for different target's locations on the (x,y)-plane. We observe that we have two distinct regions separated by a red line: for negative x-values the monostatic received power is higher whereas for positive x-values the bistatic received power is higher. However, the above received power comparison does not consider one of the main challenges occurring in monostatic sensing such as the high self-interference occurring at the monostatic receiver antenna array. This results in a received signal corrupted by self-interference which may drastically affect the sensing performance.

Fig. 11: SNR for bistatic and SSINR for quasi-monostatic and monostatic sensing settings in dB versus target's location on the x-axis with $y=-2$ for different values of Tx-Rx isolation.

In order to show the effect of self-interference and compare different sensing settings in terms of performances, we consider a target moving along the x-axis with $y=-2$. In the following simulation figures, we consider the parameters provided in Table 2, where simulation parameters have been selected for an indoor or a small BS. We consider the system model similar to the model provided in [14] where the self-interference is represented by an additional signal of strength depending on the isolation between Tx and Rx. In Fig. 11, we plot the Signal-to-

Noise Ratio (SNR) for the bistatic setting without self-interference and Signal-to-Self-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SSINR) for quasi-monostatic and monostatic settings with self-interference for different values of isolation between the Tx and the Rx versus target's location across the x-axis. We observe that the quasi-monostatic setting gives the highest SSINR compared to the monostatic setting for negative x target's locations. For positive x values, we expect the highest performance for the bistatic setting.

Fig. 12: NMSE of the localization function of angle-of-arrival estimates for bistatic/quasi-monostatic/monostatic sensing versus target's location on the x-axis with $y=-2$ for different values of Tx-Rx isolation.

In Fig. 12, we can see the normalized mean square errors (NMSEs) of the localization function of AoA estimates for the considered sensing settings for different values of Tx-Rx isolation. The localization functions are estimated using the Multiple Signal Classification (MUSIC) method introduced in [15]. We observe that for negative x values of the target's locations, the quasi-monostatic sensing outperforms the monostatic and the bistatic settings. The monostatic setting fails to estimate the localization function especially for lower Tx-Rx isolation values. Interestingly, even though the SSINR ratio of the monostatic can be higher (e.g., Tx-Rx isolation of 20dB) than the SNR value for the bistatic setting, the estimation algorithm may completely fail due to the presence of the interference part in the received signal model. On the contrary, as the received signal of the bistatic sensing does not contain any self-interference, it can give better performance even for smaller SNR values as compared to the SSINR values of the monostatic setting. For positive x-values of the target's location, the bistatic sensing gives the best performance as compared to all other settings. From another point, the performance of the bistatic is rather 'flat' compared to the quasi-monostatic, i.e. its worst performance values are much better than the worst values of the quasi-monostatic. It should also be noted that quasi-monostatic will not perform well in practice at low frequencies, due to the duplication of large antennas, which limits its deployment.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this article, we have presented an overview of ISAC topologies and highlighted the problem of maintaining sensing requirements during a sensing session. In fact, a topology switching may be necessary when an ongoing sensing task is confronted with different events such as object mobility or

deterioration of sensing performance. To determine the functions capable of switching an ISAC topology, we have described an ISAC architecture comprising control and processing functions and illustrated how they can interact to exchange sensing measurements and Tx/Rx SU configurations. An iterative approach has been described where a sensing control function in the ISAC architecture can decide, on the basis of the received sensing measurements (e.g. RSRP, ToA, SNR, AoA, RTT) and continuous analysis, which topology to switch to (or maintain). In terms of performance, bistatic sensing is considered the ISAC topology that provides the optimum results due to absence of self-interference.

It is also worth noting that a more complete assessment of the topology switching needs to be carried out considering that some data related to sensing results needs to be buffered by the sensing units during a topology switch, and further this would incur delay. Therefore, as for future work, the authors plan to include a latency analysis of the end-to-end sensing architecture, including the potential delay caused by topology switching, data buffering and transfer requirements.

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